

**INTERNATIONAL UNION FOR
PREHISTORIC AND
PROTOHISTORIC SCIENCES
(UISPP) –
30th COMMISSION**

GORJ COUNTY COUNCIL

**ROMANIAN ACADEMY
INSTITUTE OF ARCHAEOLOGY
"VASILE PÂRVAN" BUCHAREST -
CENTRE OF THRACOLOGY**

**GORJ COUNTY MUSEUM
"ALEXANDRU ȘTEFULESCU"
TÂRGU JIU**

PROGRAMME

**17TH INTERNATIONAL COLLOQUIUM
OF FUNERARY ARCHAEOLOGY**

**BORDER GUARDS OF THE PASSES,
FROM THE FORTRESSES AND THE GRAVES.
THE BRONZE AND IRON AGES**

**Târgu Jiu, Gorj County (Romania)
4th-7th October 2018**

Organizing Committee:

**Prof. dr. Valeriu Sîrbu
President
30th Commission UISPP**

**Dr. Dumitru Hortopan
Vicepresident
Manager GCM**

**Prof. dr. Cristian Schuster
General Secretary
Centre of Thracology**

A close watch on the Tisa: the Early Iron Age necropolis Stubarlija, Serbia

Marija Ljuština, Ivan Ninčić, Teodora Radišić (Serbia)

Serbian part of the Danube Basin in the Late Hallstatt period does not reveal a picture of cultural unity. The communities from the 6th-5th centuries BC went through substantial changes during that period. Disintegration of the great Basarabi cultural complex at the end of the 6th century BC led to the formation of different cultures and cultural groups. One of those groups is the Srem/Syrmia group of the west Balkan complex as defined by M. Garašanin (1973). It was connected with a number of flat skeletal graves with rich inventory - Certosa fibulae, glass beads, segmented belts, long iron spearheads, from Syrmia and eastern Slavonia, dated to the 5th and the 4th century BC.

During the 1990s in south Bačka, near the village Mošorin, some 800m eastwards from the Feudvar settlement site, which is situated on the right bank of the Tisa River, the Stubarlija necropolis was excavated. This is the first necropolis of the Syrmia group that was defined as such with certainty. The Stubarlija necropolis moved northern boundaries of the Syrmia group. It contained five skeletal graves with inventory which included pottery finds with tradition of the Bosut group, and imported goods: Certosa fibulae, glass beads and cowry shells.

The imported material confirms strong relations with other regions, which is not surprising having in mind the position of site – directly on the lower Tisa. Tracing the origin of the Certosa fibulae from the territory of the Syrmia group, P. Medović, the explorer of the site, marked the region of nowadays Slovenia. The fibulae can be explained both as a direct import from the Eastern Alpine region and as a product of local workshops, under strong influence from the west, the Sava River being the main communication route. However, the importance of the Tisa as an important transversal northward should not be neglected.

There is only a limited possibility to establish a solid chronological frame for the skeletal graves at Stubarlija. According to P. Medović, the necropolis is dated at the 4th and the beginning of the 3rd century BC. But material confirmations for such chronological positioning are not as firm as they must be. Having this in mind, generally earlier dates should be taken into consideration.

Exotic goods from the Early Iron Age necropolis Stubarlija, Serbia, as indicators of cultural contacts

Marija Ljuština, Teodora Radišić, Ivan Ninčić (Serbia)

The Early Iron Age necropolis Stubarlija is situated near the village of Mošorin in south Bačka. It contained five skeletal graves attributed to the Srem/Syrmia group. The grave inventory included pottery finds, Certosa fibulae, glass beads and cowry shells. Apart from the pottery finds with traditions of the local Bosut group, other finds are considered to be imported goods. In this paper we will focus on cowry shells, which are the unique finds which have not been recorded on other sites in the territory of the Syrmia group.

Cowry shells were found only in one grave of this necropolis. It is grave 1 which contained skeleton of a female, lying in supine position, with arms on the upper part of the